

PARADIGM CHANGES IN RURAL MOUNTAIN TOURISM AS A RESULT OF THE ATTRACTIVENESS GENERATED BY MOUNTAIN PRODUCTS AND LOCAL GASTRONOMIC POINTS

Vasile AVĂDĂNEI^{1,2*}, Ioan SURDU¹, Lidia AVĂDĂNEI²

¹ Center for Mountain Economy “CE-MONT” of the National Institute of Economic Research
“Costin C. Kirițescu”, Romanian Academy

² Creative Innovative Business Incubation Center, Romanian Mountain Forum

* Corresponding author: vasileavadanei2004@yahoo.com; +40 721811362

Abstract

For the “post-Covid era” our aim is to identify solutions for social resilience and the restoration of direct interpersonal contacts affected by the constraints of interaction and isolation established at national and international levels during the COVID 19 pandemic. An important role in achieving this goal is expected from the rural mountain tourism, which preserves traditional elements that mitigate the shocks of change during the transition to post-modern society and which can serve a special strategy.

Relatively recently, a new form of support for rural mountain tourism has been established, gastronomic tourism, based on the valorization of mountain products and the foundation of the local gastronomic points. These increase the attractiveness of the rural mountain space by intensifying people’s travels and interactions between hosts and guests.

In this paper, our aim is to highlight how the interaction interface between the two parties is modified, with local cultural support as a catalyst. Elements of cultural, emotional, and spiritual interaction revealed that these have to be well prepared to reduce possible unpredictable negative reactions in the host-guest relationship. In this form of tourism, the action moves predominantly to the householder’s yard, which implies a voluntary invasion of the host family’s universe.

In addition to the prepared food products, guests seek and want to find out information about the host family, about culture, customs, local traditions, etc.

Hosts care about their image and prepare an environment that is as attractive and as hospitable as possible.

All of this requires efforts and compromises on the part of the hosts, by partially giving up the privacy of their own households. Moreover, the host must have the ability to communicate funny stories and histories to the guests, framed in elements of culture and civilization. A pertinent and well-founded study requires a specific theoretical approach to the phenomena to highlight cultural and emotional particularities, to describe in detail elements of the domestic activity continuum in order to transform them into elements of tourist attraction and to capitalize on them in the diversity of hospitality.

Keywords: *Mountain product, local gastronomic point, the relationship between “house” and “home”, emotional communication, the “host” – “guest” relationship.*

INTRODUCTION

The pandemic period with restrictive measures has created imbalances in interpersonal communication systems. These imbalances tend to persist even after the restrictions are removed. As a result, a deficit in communication and social and interpersonal interaction persists. People are afraid of each other and have developed a social isolation syndrome.

There has been an intensification of communication on the internet, which certain social categories find more difficult to assimilate. There have also been deficiencies in communication between generations due to the interference between the two support mechanisms: through the virtual internet/mobile environment and directly through spoken language.

In a balanced social system, there must be a harmonization of interpersonal relationships and an interaction based on cultural support capable of achieving inter-human integration.

The solutions we need to resort to in order to get things back on a balanced track help us improve interpersonal communication and restore the emotional potential of communication so that culture can once again become a way of regulating both the individuals of a generation and the social groups that the generations form.

The socio-human research that we conducted on the occasion of projects addressed to young people (Avădănei 2021a, 2021b) highlighted the fact that tourism is exactly on the natural path of entrepreneurial and consumer solutions for our needs for relaxation, entertainment, well-being, etc. as well as social communication needs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Arnesen (2022) points out that for any person who adheres to the practice of Mobility, a distinction is systematically made between “house” and “home”. This involves an emotional interaction with the hosts and with the space intended for hospitality. As a result, attitudes towards mobility change, tourist flows develop in areas that tell stories about certain places. Hannam et al. (2006) pointed out that a shock of mobility can be recorded because they are the basis of personal motivations: free time, work, development of interpersonal relationships, creation of social networks. Several authors consider that this intensification of mobility is transformed into recreational commuting (Overvag 2010; Arnesen 2014; Ellingsen 2017; Ellingsen & Nilsen 2021). This commuting makes the connection between an urban environment and a rural environment (Overvåg 2010; Arnesen et al. 2012). If this commute develops mainly on the recreational component and at the workplace, we can talk about changes in the meanings of the term mobilities and demographic developments.

The status of the tourist in search of relaxation or work adapts to the time he gives to the place/stopover of interaction (Ellingsen and Nilsen 2021). It is curious and interesting that the host invests in the residence, while the tourist uses it. It should also be noted that the host is captive to his own space, while the tourist has freedom of expression (pro or against) in different environments.

In human existence there is always an inner impulse to build. The host builds both for himself and to provide the resources necessary for daily living. Heidegger (2001) shows that people does not live to build, but construction is a way of living. Galent (2006) says that housing is a familiarization of space, and the building is part of the personalization process. If an entrepreneur wants to build a guesthouse, this is different from his domicile. It is a new building in which he gathers a leisure landscape and defines a place of recreation for the guest. He builds a way of living, and the guest have to learn to live. Housing is a process of mutual accommodation, a coexistence between the arranged space and the being who comes to be a guest. Both the space and the being change their lifestyle. Thus, appears the dichotomy between “house” and “home”. “Home” is built on the frequency of use and the well-being, the comfort of the occupant. Together the two concepts define a semiotics of dwelling. These elements of differentiation are best perceived when we travel. As hosts we build these spaces for

hypothetical guests. But, when we are the tourists, we consume this representation built by hypothetical hosts for us.

METHODOLOGY

Recently, two instruments have appeared in the Romanian rural tourism landscape that bring back into discussion both the sales-purchase process and rural tourism. They are the “Mountain Product” and the “Local Gastronomic Points”.

The mountain product is an optional quality certificate, addressed to food products that are formed and developed in the mountain area (ANZM 2022).

The local gastronomic point is a less demanding form of public catering in which the host comes in the way of the guest with the food that he usually prepared for himself (ANSVSA 2023).

They will help us understand how the people involved interact. A network of lines and nodes is built. The familiarity is sought through which some of the nodes have a greater “shine” due to compatibility with one’s own lifestyle. We will find that due to modernization and, implicitly, globalization, a population flow between rural and urban areas is manifested in which people of working age migrate to dynamic and attractive urban centers.

But modern life creates excesses and surpluses that lead to lifestyle imbalances. In these conditions they will allocate more time for recreation. By propagation they must allocate time, money, mobility (travel) to rural landscapes. This is the driving support of rural development capable of building recreational facilities in line with the lifestyle expected by townpeoples. This process intensifies or diminishes in correlation with the creation and distribution of wealth.

Also, wealth determines an evolutionary change in lifestyle, in the forms of control over owned goods, time and space. Tastes, preferences, decision-making methods change, ideals, aspirations regarding how to live, what constitutes a good life change. In this context, the term “home” becomes relevant. “Home” can be summer at the seaside, winter skiing, vacation in scenic paradises, historical or cultural itineraries.

Papers on tourism treat the social component of accommodation as a black box. Priority was given to the intervention of geographers who carried out a mapping in space-time coordinates of everyday life. And yet sociologists have failed to make the connection between the spatiality of permanent residence and people’s desire to move from one event to another. Instead, the motivational elements of mobilities have been identified as forms of economic, social, and political life.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Starting from these elements, destination tourism was reconsidered in the coordinates house - home - dwelling. A dwelling is a social unit (Arnesen 2022), elevated to the rank of institution, that has as its support a household, a living environment that offers security, rest, tranquility, happiness. For other beneficiaries and hypothetical users, the dwelling is a place of origin or a refuge. The latter is determined by an anxiety or an escape into a realm of family memories. If the level of rigorous connection is exceeded, several places can be imagined that form an animated network of flows. This model is favored by transport systems and organizing the time for traveling, visiting, resting, dining, admiring the landscape, savoring each of these elements. We are witnessing the space expansion through the increase in mobility in which we use a set of houses that causes a continuous change in lifestyle.

Some models consider this lifestyle change as a process of accommodation in a complex network, driven by a “familial locomotive” (Williams et. al 2004). The purchase of a house has a symbolic meaning: a room in a hotel, a seat at a restaurant, a weekend at an agritourism guesthouse, a meal at a local gastronomic point.

We want to highlight the fact that the relationship between host and guest can manifest itself on a variety of levels:

- at the hotel we are greeted by the hotelier who fulfills a protocol role. A package of instructions gives us the strictly necessary information, or the useful ones, or the ones requested by the client. But, a threshold of emotional communication is not crossed and familiarity is not used, even if there have been previous visits.

- at the agri-tourism guesthouse, the host welcomes us and offers us a package of events that are appropriate and at the level of the requirements of such forms of reception. Again, the level of familiarity is very strictly maintained. The families staying receive products generated by the guesthouse's annexed household. But the host, in addition to the manifestations of hospitality, must also take care of the household. Basically, for limited periods of time, the host neglects his guests, who, indeed, have a package of activities at their disposal.

- at a restaurant it is the same situation: we have in front of us a package called menu, based on which we express our comfort in choosing the dishes that seem interesting to us. Music, most of the time, forces itself to maintain a drive determined by the culture of the fiddlers, which, *nolens – volens*, we digest or endure.

- for the holiday package, guesthouses prepare a standard format of dishes that we force ourselves to accept within the same range limited by extremes: we agree to taste traditional dishes within the limits of digestibility; or we throw ourselves at the table in a conjunctural gastronomic assault.

At the local gastronomic point, things are completely different. The host receives us in the home he has and prepares especially for guests. Basically, we sleep in the beds where the host's family usually sleeps. We sit at the table with the host and eat what the host eats. It is true that the host announced the menu, but the quantities prepared are not exaggerated. Basically, the event has the dimensions of an agape. The communication distance is reduced to the threshold of intimacy and favors a special relationship for home and living.

Through the host - guest interaction, have place ongoing changes in the lifestyle of each part. We consider this as an opportunity to intensify interpersonal relationships in the gap caused by the isolation restrictions imposed by the pandemic. The needs for interpersonal communication, mobility, and self-esteem are satisfied through the host - guest interaction.

Local gastronomic points have this impact of the entrepreneurial attraction for a category of rural households that gain self-confidence to build a consumption concept, to fulfill a series of operating formalities, to discipline themselves on a narrow level of hygienic and sanitary restrictions.

Local gastronomic points are the best way to verify the proposed hypotheses.

The people involved, repeat the procedures and consolidate a series of procedures and stereotypes on the basis of which consolidated interpersonal relationships are built.

For the host, the local gastronomic point provides a motivation to keep clean the house and the household so that the guests feel good. On the other hand, the guests satisfy their emotional balances created both by the rural - urban movement that generates nostalgia, and by the urban - rural movement that seeks solutions for spend free time in a way desired by needs and emotional life.

The level of emotional interaction is the highest in the hospitality industry. This aspect is also argued by the reason that the host no longer has a space to retreat to his own circle of intimacy. The guests do not have this comfort either. Basically, we are dealing with a voluntary intensification of emotional and spiritual interactions through the nature of the topics of discussion addressed, through the mutual sharing of joys and sorrows.

The guests cultivate nostalgia for a fairly recent rural childhood. The hosts are happy to display in front of the guests various local souvenirs, achievements of the talents of folk craftsmen: textile objects, clothing, decorations, household items, folk costumes that they display on different occasions. Also, both the guests and the hosts learn to live, that is, to use a decorated space appropriately for the manifestation of personality attributes, which lead to the continuous adaptation of the lifestyle.

What sells a local gastronomic point is not necessarily the food it serves but rather the exchange of emotions, feelings, mutual admiration, delight. The satisfaction is mutual for both hosts and guests.

Over time, each person becomes aware that personal fulfillment is achieved mainly through mobility: the consumption of the landscape, interpersonal relationships, exchanges of messages and ideas. Galent (2006) argues that there are undercurrents that produce changes and give consistency to the act of living.

In reality, each person develops a multi-centric lifestyle on two axes: the home - work (service) axis and the time - place axis. In the defined space, meanings (semiotics) and identity (culture) are structured.

The "house" becomes a "reference complex". It interacts with emotions and transforms into "home" and creates an attachment to a typical rural area. Stedman (2006) notes that attachment is more intense for seasonal guests than for year-round guests. With this observation, we find that the scope of study is not only tourism, but also extends to long-term living due to studies, internships, temporary services.

There is a redefinition of space as nature and as cultural facilities dedicated to leisure and recreation. Through the dichotomy "house" - "home" we make a distinction between the physical structure of a building with special functional allocations and the structure of a house associated with a style and way of life anchored in the mists of time.

CONCLUSIONS

The post-pandemic period has generated an emerging flow of mobilities that restore the interpersonal communication paths that were untimely stopped during the pandemic.

Tourism has the necessary tools and means to rebuild the desire to travel.

Two new types of tourist products create conditions for emergence: the *Mountain Product* and the *Local Gastronomic Point*. These significantly reduce the distance of emotional interaction between the host and the guest and create the premises of attachments that both the host and the guest need.

Physical meetings, direct communication, access to dining and sleeping services involve covering small spaces with a size comparable to the hosts' homes. As a result, emotional transformations occur in both the host and the guest. Thus, the host's house also becomes the guest's bedroom. The guest becomes familiar with the host's home much more than with other types of tourist services, which keep the communication at an impersonal, distant, protocol level, as much as cultural customs allow.

Under these conditions, the content base of the terms "house" and "home" and even "dwelling" changes. Inter human relationships tend to cover the trends of social alienation that are increasingly manifesting themselves, both due to the pandemic and the migration of the population in search of a better-paid job and a safer life. These empty any human

interactions of emotional content and amplify depressive phenomena and fear of communication.

It is expected that tourism based on *Mountain Products and Local Gastronomic Points* will regenerate the basis of relationships and restore well-being.

Currently, the generations participating in the transfer of cultural heritage have the tools and facilities necessary for an emotional interaction favorable to the restoration of well-being, especially among the urban population, but also among the rural population.

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